

DOPAMINE RECEPTOR AND TRANSPORTER BINDING ASSOCIATED WITH SOCIAL
ANXIETY DISORDER: A META ANALYSIS

by

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Abstract

Social anxiety disorder (SAD), formerly known as social phobia, is characterized as the fear of scrutiny, embarrassment, and negative judgment by others within everyday social situations. While several risk factors such as life experiences, environment, and development cause the onset of SAD, biological factors—including genetics and brain chemistry—contribute to the etiology. Previous research discovered that the neurotransmitter dopamine (DA) plays an essential role in several psychiatric disorders, including SAD. Various studies have compared DA binding potential to receptors and transporter between patients clinically diagnosed with SAD and healthy comparisons. In this project, 30 articles were initially chosen via literature and screened using a set of defined selection criteria specific for this project. Four papers were included in a statistical analysis using effect size (Cohen's *d*) values derived or extracted from the reported results. This Senior Honors Project aimed to conduct a meta-analysis to evaluate the strength and direction of the relationship between DA binding and SAD across the analyzed studies. Statistical analysis was performed using Microsoft Excel and Meta-Mar's online software to calculate fixed-effect and random-effect models of weighted effect size across all four articles. In conclusion, the weighted effect size across the studies was negative; however, the magnitude of the effect was non-significant. The inconclusiveness may be due to the limited number of studies and multiple brain regions included in the analysis. Future neuroscientists should conduct more consistent and large-scale research for conclusive and replicable results.

Introduction

Social anxiety disorder (SAD), originally known as social phobia, is characterized by fear of scrutiny, embarrassment, and negative judgment within everyday social situations. It is officially recognized and diagnosed under the anxiety class disorders under DSM-V (Substance Abuse and Mental Health Services Administration, n.d.). SAD symptoms can vary in severity from person to person; however, some common symptoms are blushing, sweating, trembling, nausea, shortness of breath, dizziness, and lightheadedness (Social anxiety disorder (social phobia)). These symptoms can occur in any social circumstance, ranging from school presentations, work meetings, running basic errands, eating in public, or making eye contact with strangers. Some individuals have a fear so severe that their symptoms affect their daily functioning and social progression. On the other hand, others may experience the same anxiety but can still accomplish social activities.

The onset of social anxiety disorder usually begins in early adolescence, ranging from early to mid-teens. It can first develop in younger children and even adults in some other cases. Several risk factors contribute to SAD, such as stress, traumatic life experiences, and temperament (Social anxiety disorder (social phobia)). Individuals who have experienced emotional abuse, bullying, rejection, or other negative experiences are more likely to develop anxiety disorders. Additionally, individuals with a family history of SAD can also be at risk of developing the disorder themselves. Genetics, neuroanatomy, and neurochemistry contribute to the etiology of SAD. The disorder can be heritable, leaving people genetically predisposed to developing SAD. Furthermore, variations in neural structures and neurotransmission may also influence SAD symptoms.

Various studies have discovered associations between psychiatric disorders and dopamine (DA) dysfunction over the last two decades. DA plays an essential regulatory role in the central nervous system, such as regulating emotions and cognition, including thinking, understanding, and reasoning (Dong et al., 2020). In their meta-analysis, Dong et al. also concluded that patients with OCD and anxiety had reduced striatal dopamine D2 receptor binding to healthy controls. Additionally, according to Cervenka et al. (2012) in their article, patients with SAD had reduced striatal dopamine markers compared to healthy control subjects. Many studies have used PET and SPECT imaging studies, which have utilized radiotracers that compete with DA binding: [123I]- β -CIT, [123I]-IBZM, and more (Dong et al., 2020). Inspired by these preliminary studies and meta-analyses, the objective of this Senior Honors Project was to conduct a meta-analysis, specifically on studies that have observed DA binding within patients with social anxiety disorder compared to matched healthy control subjects.

In this project, 30 published studies were collected, which all reported conclusive findings of DA binding potential between patients with social anxiety disorder and healthy control participants. Four of those studies matched the defined search criteria to be included in the quantitative analysis. This Senior Honors Project determined the magnitude and direction of the overall effect across the studies. It was hypothesized that the weighted effect across the analyzed studies would show that patients with social anxiety disorder have reduced DA receptor and transporter binding potential compared to control subjects.

Methods

Study Identification

A literature search was conducted between September 1 - and 14, 2021, to collect an initial sample of articles. The search engines used consisted of PubMed, PsycInfo, and Cochrane Review. Keywords used in the search include combinations among the following: "social anxiety disorder," "social anxiety," "social phobia," "dopamine," "dopamine receptor," "dopamine function," "dopamine transporter," "striatum," and "amygdala." Through the search via the PubMed database, 15 articles were identified as potential studies. Five articles were collected from the PsycInfo search engine, and 10 articles were chosen from the search on Cochrane Review. The references of relevant studies were reviewed for additional articles that were initially not identified by the electronic literary search. In total, 30 articles were collected. All articles selected were free and open access.

Search Criteria and Selection

The initial 30 articles were initially assessed via title and abstract. Fifteen studies were chosen, then further assessed using the defined search criteria. Search criteria were defined using guidelines from the Cochrane Review handbook. The type of population, methodology, and study designs were determined to narrow the type of studies that were to be included in the analysis (McKenzie, JE et al., 2022). The inclusion criteria for the selected studies were

1. The population of the study should be participants diagnosed with social anxiety or social phobia via DSM IV criteria and healthy comparisons,
2. Patients were un-medicated or are not undergoing pharmacological intervention or therapy, and

3. The study designs of the articles should observe the association between dopaminergic factors of healthy participants versus diagnosed patients.

Specific age groups, gender, ethnicity, race, and socioeconomic background were not considered. Interventional studies, such as pharmacotherapy and behavioral therapy, were excluded. Studies with social anxiety as a comorbidity to other conditions (i.e., fibromyalgia, Parkinson's disease, autism, PTSD.) were also excluded. The consort diagram below illustrates the selection process and the final pool of articles chosen to be included in the statistical analysis (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Consort diagram of the selection and exclusion process for the selected pool of studies.

Statistical Analysis

Data were extracted from the selected studies. Table 1 reveals the study design, sample sizes, summarized results, and overall conclusions from selected studies. The effect size Cohen's d was calculated using the online calculator "Practical Meta-Analysis Effect Size Calculator" (Wilson, n.d.), shown in Table 2 of the results section. Statistical analysis was performed with Microsoft Excel with calculations using the guidance of "Introduction to Meta-Analysis" and "Practical Meta-Analysis" (Borenstein et al., 2007; Stewart, 2017). Another analysis was performed with an online meta-analysis software, Meta-Mar (<https://www.meta-mar.com/smd>). The online software self-calculated and used the effect sizes Hedge's g instead of Cohen's d . Fixed-effect and random-effect models were calculated and plotted on a forest plot (Figure 2). Data from both analyses were compared for consistencies and whether converging data would reveal significant results.

Results

Reported findings

Table 1 reveals the study design, sample sizes, summarized results, and overall conclusions from selected studies. Three out of the five studies reported that their results suggest that dopamine dysfunction is associated with social anxiety disorder. Studies 1 and 2 concluded that patients with SAD have significantly lower striatal DA binding than matched control participants. Study 4 reports a medium effect size that revealed higher D2 receptor binding in the orbitofrontal cortex in SAD patients than in controls. Studies 3 and 4 reported non-significant differences in DA binding between the two groups.

Table 1. Selected studies with their reported study designs, sample sizes, results, and conclusions about DA binding potential between patients with SAD and healthy controls.

Study ID	Article Title	Study Design	Participants	Results	Conclusions
1	Dopamine Reuptake Site Densities in Patients with Social Phobia	Comparison of patients with social phobia and healthy subjects by measuring the density of dopamine reuptake sites.	11 patients with social phobia and 11 control subjects	Striatal dopamine reuptake site densities were markedly lower in the patients with social phobia than in the comparison subjects	Results indicate that social phobia may be associated with a dysfunction of the striatal dopaminergic system
2	Low Dopamine D2 Receptor Binding Potential in Social Phobia	Comparing patients with diagnosed SAD to healthy subjects.	10 participants with SAD and ten control subjects	Mean D(2) receptor binding potential was significantly lower in the subjects with social phobia than in the comparison subjects.	Generalized social phobia may be associated with low binding of [(123)I]IBZM.
3	Dopamine Transporters, D2 Receptors, and Dopamine Release in Generalized Social Anxiety Disorder	Comparison of GSAD and healthy subjects using SPECT and PET.	15 unmedicated adults with GSAD and 13 controls	There were no significant demographic differences between samples or between the subsamples of GSAD and HC subjects.	D2 receptor binding was non-significantly lower in the GSAD group, in the same direction as prior significant findings but with a lesser magnitude of effect.
4	Extra-striatal dopamine D2-receptor availability in social anxiety disorder	Comparison of SAD subjects to healthy subjects. Two-tailed one-way independent ANCOVAs used to examine differences in D2-R availability between groups	12 outpatients with SAD and 16 control subjects	Region-based analysis showed a medium effect size of higher D2-R in OFC in patients with SAD	These preliminary results suggest that an aberrant extra-striatal dopamine system may be part of the disease mechanism in SAD.
5	Expression and co-expression of serotonin and dopamine transporters in social anxiety disorder: a multi tracer positron emission tomography study	Examine the intra-regional co-expression of SERT and DAT in patients with SAD, as compared with healthy controls	Twenty-seven patients with SAD and 43 healthy controls.	SAD patients, as compared to HC, had no significant between-group differences in DAT binding levels.	There was no significant difference in DAT binding potential between SAD patients and healthy controls.

Effect size data

Effect sizes were obtained using standardized mean differences (d) from the reported values across the study samples using a web-based effect size calculator (Wilson, n.d.). The group differences were calculated as the DA binding potential of healthy control minus the DA

binding potential of patients with social anxiety disorder. The derived effect sizes are showcased below in Table 2. Additionally, Table 2 reports the group means, standard deviations, and sample sizes used to calculate the effect sizes for each article. One article (Hjorth et al., 2019) was omitted from the analysis due to missing variables, which caused difficulty in deriving Cohen's *d* from the study data.

Table 2. Group averages, standard deviations, and sample sizes from each study.

Study ID	Authors	Year	Region/Test	SAD mean	SAD SD	SHC N	HC means	HC SD	HC N	Cohen's <i>d</i>
1	Tiihonen et. al	1997	Striatum	10.05	1.2	11	11.64	1.29	11	1.2245
2	Schneier et. al	2000	Striatum	93.6	29.8	10	133.5	38.2	10	1.1647
3	Schneier et. al	2009	Striatum ([123]β-CIT SPECT)	7.69	1.12	15	7.62	0.91	13	-0.0681
3	Schneier et. al	2009	Striatum ([11C]Raclopride PET)	13	3.7	15	13.8	3.2	12	0.2293
4	Plaven-Sigray et. al	2017	LFC	0.93	0.27	12	0.78	0.32	16	-0.5502
4	Plaven-Sigray et. al	2017	MFC	0.88	0.24	12	0.75	0.23	16	-0.5549
4	Plaven-Sigray et. al	2017	OFC	0.99	0.28	12	0.76	0.27	16	-0.8386
4	Plaven-Sigray et. al	2017	ACC	0.93	0.21	12	0.91	0.24	16	-0.0878
4	Plaven-Sigray et. al	2017	Insula	1.48	0.34	12	1.34	0.34	16	-0.4118
4	Plaven-Sigray et. al	2017	Amygdala	1.98	0.28	12	1.87	0.31	16	-0.3695
4	Plaven-Sigray et. al	2017	Hippocampus	0.89	0.13	12	0.81	0.18	16	-0.4977

Meta-analysis

Statistical analyses calculated effect sizes using Microsoft Excel and Meta-Mar's online meta-analysis software. In Table 2, the weighted fixed-effect size was calculated. Table 3 reports the weighted-random effect size across the four studies. Both fixed and random effect sizes were negative, with a magnitude of 0.139. The confidence intervals were at 95%, ranging from -0.16 or -0.11. The z-value was -11.0, while the p-values—both one-tailed and two-tailed—were also low to be rounded as 0.

Table 2. The pooled fixed-effect average across all studies. Z-score and p-value were also reported.

Fixed Effect	
Effect size	-0.139493
Variance	0.00016
SE	0.012662
CI95%_lower	-0.164311
CI95%_upper	-0.114675
Z-value	-11.01639
p-value (1-tailed)	0
p-value (2-tailed)	0

Table 3. The pooled random-effect average across all studies. Z-score and p-value were also reported.

Random Effect	
Effect size	-0.139493
Variance	0.00016033
SE	0.01266233
CI95%_lower	-0.164311

CI95%_upper	-0.114675
Z-value	-11.01639
p-value (1-tailed)	0
p-value (2-tailed)	0

Table 4 displays the generated results for the Meta-Mar online software. Hedge's g was calculated instead of Cohen's d values in Table 1. The effect size was calculated as HC mean binding potential minus SAD mean binding potential, and the weighted fixed and random effect sizes were derived from each study. Moreover, Table 5 reports the weighted fixed and random models across all studies, including the standard error of g , 95% upper bound and lower bound confidence intervals, z-scores, and p-values. Lastly, Figures 2 and 3 are forest plots for the effect size of each study and the overall weighted fixed and random effect across the studies.

Table 4. Data from Meta-Mar online software. Hedge's g from each study was calculated, along with the standard error, confidence intervals, and weighted fixed vs. random models.

Study ID	Study name	Region (Test)	g	SE_g	g_lower	g_upper	weight(%)-fixed model	weight(%)-random model
1	Tiihonen et al.	Striatum	1.22781	0.45004	0.34574	2.10988	6.72591	7.98245
2	Schneier et al.	Striatum	1.11547	0.46321	0.20758	2.02335	6.34883	7.75859
3	Schneier et al.	Striatum ([123]β-CIT SPECT)	-0.06608	0.36800	-0.78737	0.65520	10.05884	9.51387
3		Striatum ([11C]Raclopride PET)	0.22235	0.37678	-0.51613	0.96084	9.59563	9.33933
4	Plaven-Sigra et al.	LFC	-0.48565	0.37640	-1.22339	0.25208	9.61519	9.34690
4	Plaven-Sigra et al.	MFC	-0.53872	0.37768	-1.27898	0.20154	9.54975	9.32149
4	Plaven-Sigra et al.	OFC	-0.81415	0.38639	-1.57148	-0.05682	9.12414	9.15094
4	Plaven-Sigra et al.	ACC	-0.03135	0.37078	-0.75809	0.69538	9.90853	9.45832
4	Plaven-Sigra et al.	Insula	-0.39977	0.37459	-1.13396	0.33442	9.70824	9.38269

4	Plaven-Sigray et al.	Amygdala	-0.35877	0.37385	-1.09150	0.37397	9.74682	9.39740
4	Plaven-Sigray et al.	Hippocampus	-0.48316	0.37634	-1.22078	0.25447	9.61812	9.34804

Table 5. Weighted fixed and random effect sizes across all studies. Standard error, confidence intervals, Z-score, and p-value were also reported.

	Hedges' g (SMD)	SE_g	95% CI	z-score	p-value
Fixed Effect Model	-0.13	0.117	[-0.356, 0.101]	1.094	0.273922
Random Effect Model	-0.09	0.182	[-0.448, 0.267]	0.496	0.620082

Figure 2. (left): Forest plot of the fixed-effect model of each study and the average weighted fixed effect across all studies. Figure 3. (right): Forest plot of the random-effect model of each study and the average weighted random effect across all studies.

Discussion

Four studies focused on DA binding potential in patients diagnosed with social anxiety disorder. Three studies showed that SAD patients had altered DA binding compared to the

control subjects, while the other two studies found non-significant differences in DA receptor and transporter binding. Additionally, three studies observed DA binding potential in the striatum. In contrast, the fourth study observed DA binding in more than one brain region: lateral frontal cortex, medial frontal cortex, orbitofrontal cortex, anterior cingulate cortex, insula, amygdala, and hippocampus (Plaven-Sigra et al., 2017).

Outcome Measures

The effect sizes for Study 1 (Tiihonen et al., 1997) and Study 2 (Schneier et al., 2000) were positive, which was a magnitude greater than 0.8 in both the excel analysis (Table 2) and the Meta-Mar software (Table 4). These two articles had effects that found a large, positive outcome, which suggests the patients with SAD having a large magnitude of reduced DA receptor and transporter binding compared to the healthy matched comparisons. Study 3, also by Schneier et al., carried out two different imaging studies with two different radiotracers: [123]β-CIT SPECT and [11C]Raclopride PET. The effect size for the study done with [123]β-CIT SPECT was negative, small effect with a magnitude of 0.06 in both analyses. On the other hand, their study using [11C]Raclopride PET resulted in a positive effect of 0.22 in both analyses. Both tests focused on striatal DA binding, which led to contradictory results. Lastly, Study 4 measured DA binding in seven different regions. In all areas, there was a negative effect. ACC, insula, and amygdala regions had small effect sizes, while the hippocampus, LFC, and MFC resulted in a medium effect size. Lastly, the OFC had a magnitude of 0.8, interpreted as a large effect based on Laken's benchmark values. However, Plaven-Sigra et al. reported that all other regions except OFC resulted in a small effect, while the OFC had a medium-sized effect.

Furthermore, in the fifth article by Hjorth et al., they reported that the difference in DA transporter binding was non-significant. Additionally, they did not report individual group means binding or standard deviations that would allow calculations for Cohen's *d* derivation. Therefore, the analysis did not include the DA transporter binding potential study.

Weighted Effect Sizes

The weighted fixed effect across studies showed a small negative effect with a magnitude of 0.139 in both excel and Meta-Mar analyses. For the random effect, the Excel analysis produced a small, negative effect with a magnitude of 0.139. At the same time, the Meta-Mar calculated a weighted random effect with a small, negative effect size of 0.09. The effect sizes were calculated as the difference between HC mean DA binding potential and SAD mean DA binding potential. A effect size in the positive direction would indicate that patients with SAD have reduced DA binding potential compared to the control subjects. In contrast, an effect size in the negative direction would suggest that SAD patients have higher DA binding than the control subjects. All weight effect sizes were below 0.2, which was the benchmark to be considered a "small" effect. Although both analyses reported an overall effect in the negative direction, the magnitude of the effect is non-significant. Therefore, there is no significant difference between DA binding potential between patients with SAD and healthy controls.

Conclusion

This project aimed to determine the magnitude and direction of the overall effect across several studies that have compared the dopamine binding potential between patients with SAD and healthy comparisons. It was hypothesized that the weighted effect would show that patients with social anxiety disorder have reduced DA receptor binding compared to control subjects.

However, converging evidence from this project has revealed that there is a non-significant, negative effect of dopamine receptor and transporter binding across the four studies between patients with social anxiety disorder and healthy comparisons. In conclusion, the project revealed that patients with SAD have slightly increased DA receptor binding potential compared to the health control participants, but the differences were not significant. No data from this project supported the significance of DA transporter binding between patients with SAD and healthy comparisons.

Studies about this research topic were limited, and not many met the selection criteria to be included in the analysis. Due to the limited number of studies, the small sample size may have affected the project's outcome. Future extensions of this project would be to broaden search criteria to include interventional studies and use more databases to collect a larger pool of studies. Studies reported contradictory results, but from other preliminary studies, there happens to be an association between dopamine dysfunction and social anxiety disorder. Additionally, multiple different brain regions were observed in the studies analyzed, which could have resulted in varying DA behavior. Another improvement would be to narrow DA binding potential studies to one specific brain region per analysis and not include them altogether. More research with replicable and larger-scale studies must be conducted to confirm any significant alterations in dopamine binding within patients with SAD.

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